

Obeticholic acid does not restore Western diet-induced alterations in hepatic mitochondrial respiration

Jan Melek^a, Pavla Staňková^a, Eva Peterová^b , Tumisang Edward Maseko^a,
Veronika Špalková^a, Reem Matar^a ,
Miroslav Podhola^c, Alžběta Štefela^a, Zuzana Červinková^a, Petr Pávek^d , Otto Kučera^{a,*}

^a Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

^b Department of Medical Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

^c Fingerland Department of Pathology, University Hospital in Hradec Králové, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

^d Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Charles University, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
obeticholic acid
mitochondria
respirometry
succinate

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) affects a significant portion of the global population, with mitochondrial dysfunction playing a pivotal role in its pathogenesis. Although FXR agonists such as obeticholic acid (OCA) have been studied as potential treatments for MASLD, the direct effects of OCA on the liver are still not fully understood. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of OCA in an in vivo model of MASLD.

Methods: Male C57BL/6J mice were fed a control diet (CD) or a Western diet (WD) enriched with glucose and fructose in the drinking water for 36 weeks. During the final 3 weeks, mice received OCA (5 or 10 mg/kg/day) or vehicle. Liver histology, biochemical parameters, gene expression, mitochondrial enzymes activity and mitochondrial respiration were assessed.

Results: WD-fed mice exhibited increased body and liver weights and elevated aminotransferases, none of which were altered by OCA. OCA treatment did not significantly impact steatosis, inflammation, fibrosis, or hepatic lipid content. WD feeding reduced succinate-stimulated hepatic mitochondrial respiration, associated with decreased succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) expression and activity. OCA partially restored Sdh subunits B and C expression but did not significantly improve respirometric parameters.

Conclusion: Our findings consistently demonstrate that OCA administration in an established diet-induced murine model of MASLD does not improve hepatic steatosis or inflammation. Moreover, the WD-induced decrease in succinate-stimulated mitochondrial respiration was not ameliorated by OCA.

1. Introduction

Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), a

hepatic manifestation of metabolic syndrome, is the most common chronic liver disease worldwide [1]. Numerous mechanisms are implicated in the pathology of MASLD in response to continuous lipid

Abbreviations: Actb, β -actin; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; ANOVA, analysis of variance; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; β -Ox, β -oxidation; BA, bile acid; Bcl2, B-cell lymphoma 2; Bsep, bile salt export pump; cDNA, complementary DNA; CS, citrate synthase; Col1a2, collagen type I α 2 chain; Cyp7a1, cholesterol 7 α -hydroxylase; EC₅₀, half-maximal effective concentration; ETC, electron transport chain; ETS, electron transport system; eWAT, epididymal white adipose tissue; FDA, U.S. Food and Drug Administration; GSH, reduced glutathione; H&E, hematoxylin and eosin; Hpvt, hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase; MASH, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; MC, methylcellulose; NADH, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide; NAS, NAFLD, activity score; OCA, obeticholic acid; OXPHOS, oxidative phosphorylation; Panx1, pannexin 1; PBC, primary biliary cholangitis; PM, pyruvate-malate; ROS, reactive oxygen species; RT-qPCR, quantitative reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction; S, succinate; SD, standard deviation; Sdh, succinate dehydrogenase; Shp, small heterodimer partner; Suncr1, succinate receptor 1; SUIT, substrate-uncoupler-inhibitor titration; Tgf β 1, transforming growth factor β 1; Tgr5, Takeda G-protein-coupled receptor 5; TGs, triglycerides; Timp1, tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 1; Trap1, tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated protein 1; Ucp2, uncoupling protein 2; WD, Western diet; WST-1, water-soluble tetrazolium-1.

* Correspondence to: Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Šimkova 870, Hradec Králové 500 03, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: kucerao@lfhk.cuni.cz (O. Kučera).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioph.2025.118542>

Received 19 June 2025; Received in revised form 29 August 2025; Accepted 5 September 2025

0753-3322/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Masson SAS. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

accumulation in hepatocytes [2]. Growing evidence suggests that mitochondrial dysfunction plays a significant role in the pathogenesis and progression of MASLD [3–5], potentially through disruptions in mitochondrial bioenergetics. Processes contributing to mitochondrial dysfunction include reduced electron transport chain (ETC) activity and ATP synthesis, impaired mitophagy, dysfunction of mitochondria-associated membranes, and structural alterations [6,7]. Maladaptation of antioxidant defenses, combined with ETC overload by free fatty acids, exacerbates reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and oxidative stress, thereby promoting the development of MASLD [3, 8].

The farnesoid X receptor (FXR, NR1H4 gene) is a key nuclear receptor involved in multiple metabolic pathways and is predominantly expressed in the liver, intestine, kidneys, and adrenal glands [9]. FXR serves as a pivotal regulator of multiple metabolic pathways, including bile acid (BA) homeostasis, lipid metabolism—by inhibiting lipogenesis and promoting β -oxidation—cholesterol and glucose metabolism through suppression of gluconeogenesis and enhancement of glycogen synthesis, as well as amino acid metabolism and ammonia detoxification [10]. Additionally, FXR has been shown to exert antiinflammatory effects [11]. Beyond this, FXR confers antioxidative and cytoprotective benefits, primarily through its regulation of mitochondrial function [12]. Nevertheless, the clinical implications of FXR agonists in the treatment of MASLD remain incompletely understood.

FXR agonists, particularly obeticholic acid (OCA), a semisynthetic derivative of chenodeoxycholic acid, have been explored as potential therapeutic agents for MASLD treatment [13,14]. OCA was initially considered a promising candidate for MASLD therapy based on its positive effects on inflammation [15] and fibrosis [16]. OCA exerts complex metabolic effects primarily through the FXR, with a half-maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) of 99 nM, and to a lesser extent, through the Takeda G-protein-coupled receptor 5 (Tgr5), which has an EC_{50} approximately 200 times higher (20 μ M) [17,18].

Concerns regarding potential hepatotoxicity, hepatic adverse events, and side effects—such as dose-dependent pruritus and elevated LDL cholesterol—have resulted in the termination of major clinical trials evaluating OCA in MASLD [17,18]. The FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration) has repeatedly highlighted the risk of serious liver injury associated with OCA in patients with primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) [19].

The direct effects of OCA on liver cells and mitochondrial function

remain not fully understood. Accordingly, this study primarily aimed to elucidate the impact of OCA on liver cell bioenergetics using an in vivo model of MASLD induced by a Western-style diet.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals and diets

Animals were maintained under standardized environmental conditions ($23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, relative humidity $55 \pm 10\%$, and 12–14 air exchanges per hour) with a 12-hour light-dark cycle. Food and water were available ad libitum. Male C57BL/6 J mice (27 ± 2 g; Velaz, Czech Republic) were allocated to two experimental groups ($n = 41$ – 42 per group) by simple randomization using lots. Randomization was conducted by animal facility staff who were blinded to the study design and informed only of group sizes. No stratification was applied, as all animals were obtained at the same age and exhibited comparable baseline body weights. One group received a standard control diet (CD; PicoLab RD 20, LabDiet®) and tap water, while the other group was fed a Western-style diet (WD; AIN-76A WD, TestDiet®) along with glucose (18.1 g/L) and fructose (24 g/L) in the drinking water for 36 weeks (Fig. 1A). Detailed characteristics of the WD are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Random assignment was used for both diet and treatment allocation. During the final three weeks of the experiment, mice received a daily oral gavage of either a vehicle (1% methylcellulose) or vehicle containing OCA (5 or 10 mg/kg body weight) ($n = 10$ – 20). At the study endpoint, mice were euthanized under anesthesia, and blood, epididymal fat, and liver samples were collected. Collected materials were either processed immediately on ice or flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C for subsequent analyses. Samples for RNA analysis were kept in RNAlater® (Applied Biosystems). All animals were treated in accordance with the guidelines of the Animal Welfare Body at Charles University (Prague, Czech Republic) and the International Guiding Principles for Biomedical Research Involving Animals.

2.2. Plasma analysis

Plasma was analyzed using the VetScan® Preventive Care Profile Plus panel (Abaxis, Germany).

Fig. 1. Experimental protocol and weight gain during the study investigating the effect of OCA on mitochondrial respiration in a mouse model of MASLD. A. Experimental protocol: Male C57BL/6 J mice were randomly assigned to receive either a control diet (CD, $n = 10$ – 19) or an AIN-76A Western diet (WD, $n = 10$ – 20) supplemented with glucose and fructose for 33 weeks. From weeks 34 to 36, mice were treated with OCA (5 mg/kg/day or 10 mg/kg/day) or vehicle (1% methylcellulose, MC). At the end of the experiment, mice were sacrificed, and samples were collected for further analyses. B. Weight gain curves: Body weight progression of mice fed CD (blue) and WD (red) throughout the study. Symbols indicate experimental groups: black circle, CD-MC ($n = 19$); black square, CD-OCA5 ($n = 11$); black triangle, CD-OCA10 ($n = 10$); downward-pointing triangle, WD-MC ($n = 20$); black diamond, WD-OCA5 ($n = 10$); red circle, WD-OCA10 ($n = 12$). Abbreviations: CD, control diet; MC, methylcellulose; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; OCA, obeticholic acid; WD, Western diet.

2.3. Determination of triglycerides (TGs) and cholesterol

Hepatic lipids were extracted using the chloroform–methanol method as previously described [20]. Total cholesterol and TGs were quantified using commercial kits from Roche Diagnostics GmbH (Germany), following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.4. Liver histology

Fresh liver tissue was fixed in 4 % neutral-buffered formaldehyde, embedded in paraffin, sectioned, and mounted on glass slides. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was performed using standard protocols, and liver fibrosis was assessed via Sirius Red staining. Histological evaluation was conducted by a pathologist blinded to group allocation. Steatosis, including both microvesicular and macrovesicular forms, was quantified as the percentage of affected parenchyma. Lobular inflammation was graded on a scale from 0 to 3, and fibrosis was assessed on a scale from 0 to 4, in accordance with the parameters of the NAFLD Activity Score (NAS) [21].

2.5. Preparation of tissue homogenates and supernatants

Liver homogenates were prepared as described in previous studies [5] and used for the assessment of mitochondrial respiration, reduced glutathione (GSH), and hydroxyproline content. Protein concentrations were determined using the Bradford assay [22].

2.6. Glutathione and hydroxyproline

GSH levels in the supernatant were quantified using a modified fluorometric assay [23], as previously described [24]. Liver hydroxyproline content was measured colorimetrically with minor modifications to a previously established method [5]. A 100 mg sample of 10 % liver homogenate was dried at 100 °C for 24 h, hydrolyzed in 1 mL of 6 N HCl at 110 °C for 18 h, and subsequently filtered to remove debris. Each 50 μ L aliquot was then evaporated, and the resulting pellet or standard (trans-4-hydroxy-L-proline, Sigma-Aldrich) were reconstituted in 50 μ L of distilled water. These were mixed with 450 μ L of 56 mM chloramine-T trihydrate (Sigma-Aldrich) in acetate-citrate buffer (pH 6.5) and incubated at room temperature for 25 min. To facilitate chromophore formation, Ehrlich's reagent (500 μ L), composed of 1.0 mol/L p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in an n-propanol/perchloric acid solution (2:1, v/v; Sigma-Aldrich), was added, followed by incubation at 65 °C for 20 min. Absorbance was measured at 562 nm.

2.7. High resolution respirometry

Mitochondrial respiration was assessed using high-resolution respirometry (OROBOROS Oxygraph-2k, Austria) with two substrate–uncoupler–inhibitor titrations (SUIT) protocols as previously described [5]. The measurements were conducted in 2 mL of MiRO5 medium at 37 °C. Respirometry terminology was standardized according to the COST MitoEAGLE project guidelines [25].

Liver homogenates (0.15 mg/mL protein) were analyzed using a stepwise protocol involving the sequential addition of substrates, uncouplers, and inhibitors: P (pyruvate, 5 mM), M (malate, 2 mM), D (ADP, 2.5 mM), c (cytochrome c, 10 μ M), G (glutamate, 10 mM), U (carbonyl cyanide 4-(trifluoromethoxy)phenylhydrazone [FCCP], 1.5–2 μ M), S (succinate, 50 mM), Oct (octanoylcarnitine, 0.5 mM), Rot (rotenone, 0.5 μ M), and Gp (glycerophosphate, 10 mM). Finally, antimycin A (2.5 μ M) was added, and data were corrected for residual oxygen consumption as the baseline.

2.8. Succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) and citrate synthase activity (CS) in liver homogenate

SDH activity in liver homogenates was determined spectrophotometrically using p-iodonitrotetrazolium as an artificial electron acceptor, as previously described [26]. CS activity in liver homogenates was quantified using a commercially available assay kit (Sigma-Aldrich), following the manufacturer's protocol.

2.9. RNA isolation and reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR)

Total RNA was extracted using TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized using a cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Gene expression was quantified using TaqMan Gene Expression Assays.

B-cell lymphoma apoptosis regulator (Bcl2, Mm00477631_m1); bile acid export pump (Bsep, Mm00445168_m1); collagen type I collagen type I α 2 chain (Col1a2, Mm01165186_m1); cytochrome P450 family 7 subfamily A member 1, a key regulator of bile acid synthesis (Cyp7a1, Mm00484150_m1); pannexin 1, involved in ATP release and intracellular communication (Panx1, Mm01176173_m1); small heterodimer partner, a nuclear receptor and bile acid regulator (Shp, Mm00442278_m1); succinate receptor 1 (Sucnr1, Mm00519024_m1); succinate dehydrogenase subunits (SdhA, Mm01352357_m1; SdhB, Mm00458272_m1; SdhC, Mm00481172_m1; SdhD, Mm00546511_m1), involved in the mitochondrial respiratory chain; tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 1 (Timp1, Mm01341361_m1); uncoupling protein 2, a regulator of mitochondrial membrane potential (Ucp2, Mm00627599_m1); transforming growth factor β 1, a key profibrogenic factor (Tgfb1, Mm03024053_m1); tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated protein 1 (Trap1, Mm00446003_m1).

Gene expression analysis was performed using the QuantStudio® 6 Real-Time PCR system (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Results were normalized to hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (Hprt, Mm03024075_m1) and β -actin (Actb, Mm02619580_g1) RNA expression. Gene expression levels were calculated using the comparative Ct method ($\Delta\Delta$ Ct) and expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from 7–10 independent biological replicates.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism® version 10.4 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Data are presented as mean \pm SD or violin plots. Normality of data distribution was assessed prior to hypothesis testing. For normally distributed data, differences among groups were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Holm–Sidak's or Tukey's multiple comparisons test. For nonparametric data, the Kruskal–Wallis test was applied, followed by Dunn's multiple comparisons test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Morphological parameters, plasma biochemistry, liver triglycerides and cholesterol

Male C57BL/6 J mice, starting with an initial weight of 27 ± 2 g, showed a significant weight increase in the WD group compared to the CD group (Fig. 1B). Weight gain remained consistent across all treatment groups during weeks 34–36. Furthermore, liver weight and epididymal white adipose tissue (eWAT) weight, as well as kidney weight, were significantly higher in the WD group (liver and eWAT: $p < 0.0001$; kidney: $p < 0.001$) at week 36 (Table 1). OCA administration did not significantly alter overall body weight or the weights of

Table 1

Baseline phenotypic and biochemical characteristics of liver and plasma in mice fed either a CD or a WD at week 36. Mice received OCA (5 mg/kg/day or 10 mg/kg/day) during the final 3 weeks.

	Parameter	CD-MC	CD-OCA 5	CD-OCA 10	WD-MC	WD-OCA 5	WD-OCA 10
Phenotype	Body weight, g	33.0 ± 3.35	33.0 ± 3.83	34.3 ± 2.58	45.05 ± 4.38 ****	46.5 ± 5.02 ****	45.83 ± 4.59 ****
	Liver weight, g	1.39 ± 0.16	1.43 ± 0.20	1.47 ± 0.14	3.33 ± 0.76 ****	3.65 ± 0.85 ****	3.19 ± 0.75 ****
	Epididymal fat weight, g	0.73 ± 0.35	0.64 ± 0.19	0.92 ± 0.47	2.11 ± 0.53 ****	2.51 ± 0.62 ****	2.13 ± 0.34 ****
	Liver TGs, μmol/g	1.20 ± 0.41	1.12 ± 0.52	1.42 ± 0.64	12.53 ± 2.56 ****	12.2 ± 2.80 ****	11.38 ± 2.15 ****
	Liver CHOL, μmol/g	0.48 ± 0.07	0.45 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.09	4.77 ± 1.24 ****	4.08 ± 1.56 ****	3.85 ± 0.99 ****
Plasma biochemistry	ALT, μkat/L	0.36 ± 0.30	0.27 ± 0.08	0.3 ± 0.12	3.3 ± 1.01 ****	3.3 ± 1.69 ***	3.8 ± 2.65 ****
	AST, μkat/L	0.89 ± 0.39	0.65 ± 0.09	0.69 ± 0.09	3.01 ± 1.19 ***	3.12 ± 1.42 **	4.52 ± 5.06 **

Notes: All comparisons were performed between each treatment group and the control group (CD-MC) using one-way ANOVA or the Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Holm–Sidak’s or Dunn’s post hoc multiple comparison tests. Results are expressed as means ± SD, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 and ****p < 0.0001 (n = 10–20 per group). ^a includes one outlier (3.17 ± 2.07 without outlier). Abbreviations: ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; CD, control diet; CHOL, cholesterol; MC, methylcellulose; OCA, obeticholic acid; TGs, triglycerides, WD, Western diet.

individual tissues, including the liver and eWAT.

Plasma levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) were elevated in the WD group (p < 0.0001 and p < 0.001, respectively), but were not influenced by OCA administration (Table 1). There were no significant differences in bilirubin levels within the CD and WD groups (data not shown).

Liver triglyceride and cholesterol contents were significantly elevated in the WD group (p < 0.0001); however, OCA administration had no effect on these lipid levels (Table 1).

3.2. Steatosis, lobular inflammation, and fibrosis

The WD group exhibited significantly greater steatosis (p < 0.0001)

and lobular inflammation (p < 0.05) compared to the CD group (Fig. 2A-B and Supplementary Table 2). OCA treatment had no significant effect on histological features in the CD group. Similarly, in the WD group, OCA did not significantly alter steatosis, lobular inflammation, or fibrosis (Table 1).

3.3. Parameters of liver oxidative stress (GSH) and fibrosis (hydroxyproline)

The hepatic hydroxyproline content—a biochemical marker of fibrosis—was significantly elevated in the WD group compared to the CD group (Fig. 2C). OCA treatment did not attenuate this increase. A trend toward reduced GSH levels was observed in the WD group, with partial

Fig. 2. WD feeding induces hepatic steatosis, inflammatory changes, and mild fibrosis compared to a CD over 36 weeks. A. Representative histological images of liver sections from male C57BL/6J mice after 36 weeks of dietary intervention, with OCA administered during the final 3 weeks. Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining illustrates hepatic tissue architecture in mice fed a CD, WD, or WD with OCA (10 mg/kg/day). Blue arrows indicate regions of inflammatory cell infiltration. Sirius red staining highlights collagen deposition (red arrows). CD (n = 6); CD-OCA5 (n = 6); CD-OCA10 (n = 6); WD-MC (n = 17); WD-OCA5 (n = 10); WD-OCA10 (n = 12). B. Histopathological assessment of steatosis, lobular inflammation, and fibrosis after 36 weeks of WD feeding, evaluated using the NAFLD activity score (NAS). Steatosis is expressed as the percentage of affected tissue, while lobular inflammation and fibrosis were scored on scales of 0–3 and 0–4, respectively (n = 10–20 per group). C. Hepatic hydroxyproline levels and reduced glutathione (GSH) concentrations at week 36, normalized to protein content (n = 6–8 per group). Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis tests, followed by Holm–Sidak’s or Dunn’s post hoc comparisons. Data are shown as means ± SD; *p < 0.05, ****p < 0.0001. Abbreviations: CD, control diet; GSH, reduced glutathione; H&E, Hematoxylin and Eosin; NAS, NAFLD activity score; MC, methylcellulose; OCA, obeticholic acid; WD, Western diet.

restoration following OCA treatment (Fig. 2C).

3.4. Gene expression

3.4.1. FXR and the regulation of BAs

To verify activation of FXR, we analyzed mRNA expression of essential FXR target genes. Administration of OCA (10 mg/kg/day) significantly upregulated expression of small heterodimer partner (Shp) ($p < 0.05$) and correspondingly downregulated cholesterol 7 α -hydroxylase (Cyp7a1) ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 3A-B). In addition, OCA treatment markedly increased the expression of bile salt export pump (Bsep) ($p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 3C).

3.4.2. Mitochondrial function-associated genes

The expression of succinate dehydrogenase complexes (Sdh A–D), key markers of mitochondrial function, was significantly reduced in the WD group compared to the CD group ($p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 4A–D). Notably, OCA treatment (10 mg/kg/day) attenuated the WD-induced suppression of SdhB and SdhC expression.

Furthermore, assessment of SDH enzymatic activity demonstrated a reduction in the WD group, with no evidence of a beneficial effect from OCA treatment (Fig. 4E). These findings were accompanied by WD-induced reduced expression of the mitochondrial chaperone tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated protein 1 (Trap1, $p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 5A), which is known to modulate succinate dehydrogenase activity [27]. Additionally, our findings confirmed reduced expression of succinate receptor 1 (Sucnr1) in the WD group (Fig. 5B). OCA treatment (10 mg/kg/day) increased Sucnr1 expression in the CD group, while a dose-dependent positive trend was observed in the WD group. In our model, the expression of uncoupling protein 2 (Ucp2) was significantly elevated in the WD group compared to the CD group (Fig. 5C). However, OCA treatment did not affect its expression within either the CD or WD groups.

3.4.3. Markers of fibrogenesis and apoptosis

The expression of transforming growth factor β 1 (Tgfb1), a key profibrogenic factor [28], was elevated in response to the Western diet (Fig. 6A). Tgfb1 promotes the expression of tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 1 (Timp1) [29], which was also upregulated in our model, along with another fibrosis marker, collagen type 1 α 2 chain (Col1a2)

(Fig. 6B–C). However, OCA treatment did not exert a beneficial effect on any of these markers.

The plasma membrane channel pannexin 1 (Panx1), a marker of ATP release during apoptosis [30], and Bcl-2 (B-cell lymphoma 2), an anti-apoptotic regulator, both showed increased expression in the WD group. However, OCA treatment did not alter the expression of either gene (Fig. 6D–E), consistent with our previous findings [27].

3.5. High resolution respirometry

Specific activity of CS, a widely accepted marker of mitochondrial content, did not differ significantly between the CD and WD groups, and OCA treatment exerted no effect on CS activity (Fig. 4F). In our model, succinate-dependent respiration—driven by nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) and succinate (S) as substrates within the electron transport system (ETS)—was reduced in the WD group compared to the CD group. However, OCA did not produce measurable improvement in succinate-dependent respiration (Fig. 7D). NADH-driven respiration, ETS capacity, and ketogenesis were unaffected by either WD or OCA (Fig. 7). β -oxidation remained unchanged in response to OCA.

4. Discussion

The global burden of MASLD is substantial; however, effective therapeutic options remain limited, with mitochondrial dysfunction considered an important factor in its pathogenesis [4,31]. FXR agonists continue to represent a promising therapeutic target in MASLD research [32]. OCA has been approved as a second-line therapy for PBC [33]. Additionally, its efficacy and safety have been investigated in a Phase II clinical trial involving patients with primary sclerosing cholangitis [34]. Although it seemed to be a promising therapeutic candidate for MASLD, its precise mechanisms of action remain unclear. Concerns regarding adverse effects, including hepatotoxicity, dyslipidemia, pruritus, diarrhea, constipation, and increased lithogenicity, have limited further exploration of OCA in MASLD [35]. Reports of liver function decompensation and even fatal outcomes in PBC patients prompted the FDA to impose restrictions on its use in patients with PBC at risk of liver decompensation [36]. In patients with liver impairment, OCA accumulation can reach levels up to 13 times higher than in individuals with normal liver function [37]. Animal studies using high doses of OCA in

Fig. 3. OCA demonstrates regulatory effects on bile acid-related gene expression in the mouse liver. Gene expression was analyzed at week 36 for A. Shp, a regulator of bile acid (BA) synthesis; B. Cyp7a1 (cholesterol 7 α -hydroxylase), a downstream target suppressed by Shp and C. Bsep, a bile acid transporter with anticholestatic properties. Statistical analyses were performed using a one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test. Gene expression levels were normalized to hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (Hprt) and β -actin (Actb) mRNA expression. Relative gene expression was determined using the comparative Ct ($\Delta\Delta$ Ct) method. Data are presented as violin plots showing the full distribution of 7–10 independent replicates. Each symbol represents one biological replicate. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and **** $p < 0.0001$. Abbreviations: Actb, β -actin; BA, bile acid; Bsep, bile salt export pump; CD, control diet; Cyp7a1, cholesterol 7 α -hydroxylase; Hprt, hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase; MC, methylcellulose; OCA, obeticholic acid; Shp, small heterodimer partner; WD, Western diet.

Fig. 4. WD reduces SDH activity and expression of Sdh subunits (A–D), while OCA (10 mg/kg/day) increases the expression of subunits B and C. Gene expression in the mouse liver at week 36 for (A) SdhA, (B) SdhB, (C) SdhC, and (D) SdhD. Hepatic succinate dehydrogenase (E) and citrate synthase (F) activity. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparisons test. Gene expression levels were normalized to Hprt and Actb expression. Relative gene expression was determined using the comparative Ct ($\Delta\Delta Ct$) method. Data are presented as violin plots showing the full distribution of 7–8 independent replicates. Each symbol represents one biological replicate. * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$, ns, not significant. Abbreviations: Actb, β -actin; CD, control diet; Hprt, hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase; MC, methylcellulose; OCA, obeticholic acid; Sdh, succinate dehydrogenase; WD, Western diet.

Fig. 5. WD downregulates expression of mitochondrial function-associated genes encoding the Sdh modulators Trap1 and Sucnr1, with a trend toward restoration following OCA treatment. In contrast, WD upregulates expression of Ucp2. Gene expression was analyzed in the mouse liver at week 36 for A. Trap1, B. Sucnr1, and C. Ucp2. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparisons test. Gene expression levels were normalized to hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (Hprt) and β -actin (Actb) RNA expression. Relative gene expression was determined using the comparative Ct ($\Delta\Delta Ct$) method. Data are presented as violin plots showing the full distribution of 7–10 independent replicates. Each symbol represents one biological replicate. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, and **** $p < 0.0001$. Abbreviations: Actb, β -actin; CD, control diet; Hprt, hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase; MC, methylcellulose; OCA, obeticholic acid; Sucnr1, succinate receptor 1; Trap1, tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated protein 1; Ucp2, uncoupling protein 2; WD, Western diet.

MASLD models have demonstrated FXR-dependent liver injury, characterized by interleukin-1 β -mediated effects, cholesterol accumulation, hepatic fibrosis, stellate cell activation, and, in severe cases, premature death [38].

In our study, we used established WD inducing MASLD [39]. OCA was administered for three weeks—a duration shown in several studies to be sufficient for detecting therapeutic effects. For example, short-term OCA treatment (24 days) improved steatosis and inflammation in

Fig. 6. WD increases the expression of fibrogenesis (A–C) and apoptosis (D–E) markers in the mouse liver at week 36. Gene expression was analyzed for A. Tgfb1, B. Timp1, C. Col1a2, D. Panx1, and E. Bcl2. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way ANOVA test followed by Tukey’s multiple comparisons tests. Gene expression levels were normalized to hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase (Hprt) and β -actin (Actb) RNA expression. Relative gene expression was determined using a comparative Ct method ($\Delta\Delta Ct$) method. Data are presented as violin plots showing the full distribution of 7–10 independent replicates. Each symbol represents one biological replicate. * $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.001$. Abbreviations: Actb, β -actin; Bcl2, B-cell lymphoma 2; CD, control diet; Col1a2, collagen type I $\alpha 2$ chain; Hprt, hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase; OCA, obeticholic acid; Panx1, pannexin 1; Tgfb1, transforming growth factor $\beta 1$; Timp1, tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases 1; WD, Western diet.

Fig. 7. WD attenuates succinate-activated mitochondrial respiration in the liver of WD-fed mice. Mitochondrial respiration was assessed in liver homogenates from mice fed CD or WD for 36 weeks, with OCA administered during the final 3 weeks, using high-resolution respirometry (Oroboros Oxygraph-2k). Respiratory Parameters: A. PM (OXPHOS): Oxidative phosphorylation capacity supported by pyruvate (P) and malate (M) as substrates, reflecting complex I activity. B. NADH (OXPHOS): Oxidative phosphorylation state driven by NADH-generating substrates (pyruvate, glutamate, malate). C. NADH (ETS): Maximal electron transfer system (ETS) capacity fueled by NADH substrates in the uncoupled state. D. NADH + S (ETS): Combined ETS capacity using both NADH (complex I) and succinate (complex II) as electron donors, reflecting overall mitochondrial respiratory efficiency. E. Ketogenesis: Respiration associated with ketogenesis-linked substrates (octanoylcarnitine), indicative of β -oxidation flux. F. β -Ox: Fatty acid β -oxidation-driven respiration assessed using octanoylcarnitine. G. OXPHOS Capacity: Comprehensive mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation capacity with all substrates and saturating ADP. H. ETS Capacity: Maximal respiration in the uncoupled state with all electron donors, reflecting the upper limit of mitochondrial respiratory chain capacity. Statistical analyses were performed using one-way ANOVA or the Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Holm–Sidak’s or Dunn’s post hoc multiple comparison tests. * $p < 0.05$. Violin plots illustrate the full distribution of the data; each symbol corresponds to one sample. CD (n = 13); CD-OCA 5 (n = 9); CD-OCA 10 (n = 8); WD-MC (n = 13); WD-OCA 5 (n = 6); WD-OCA 10 (n = 12). Abbreviations: β -Ox, β -oxidation; CD, control diet; ETS, electron transport system; MC, methylcellulose; NADH, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide; OCA, obeticholic acid; OXPHOS, oxidative phosphorylation; PM, pyruvate and malate; WD, Western diet.

metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH) models [40], and 3–4 weeks of treatment demonstrated FXR-dependent reductions in hepatic steatosis [41] as well as synergistic benefits with glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists in metabolic disease and MASH models [42]. This timeframe has thus been validated in prior literature and is adequate for capturing OCA's therapeutic potential.

We selected an OCA dose of 5–10 mg/kg/day to approximate human therapeutic exposure while avoiding toxicity [43]. In contrast, many experimental studies in mice use doses of 20–40 mg/kg/day, which result in highly supraphysiological systemic exposures. In mice, a dose of 25 mg/kg/day yields systemic exposure ~12-fold higher than in humans at the maximum 10 mg/day (human $C_{max} \approx 0.13 \mu\text{M}$; ~1.6 μM at 12 \times) [36,44]. Moreover, due to extensive first-pass extraction, hepatocytes are exposed to markedly higher OCA concentrations than other tissues. Indeed, human hepatic exposure to BAs has been estimated to be physiologically ~6- to 8-fold greater than in extrahepatic tissues [45]. Notably, in our HepaRG human hepatocyte-like cell model micromolar concentrations of OCA showed reduced viability by WST-1 assays after 48 h (Supplementary Figure 1). Together with reports that 40 mg/kg/day OCA can aggravate fibrosis via FXR-mediated apoptosis in cholestatic models, our pilot data in a WD-induced MASLD mouse model showed pathological aminotransferase elevations at 30 mg/kg/day OCA (Supplementary Figure 2), indicating that supraphysiologic dosing may inflate apparent efficacy while compromising safety. In our experiment, we therefore focused on lower, clinically more relevant doses to better reflect the translational potential of OCA's metabolic effects.

In our model, the FXR metabolic pathway was enhanced by OCA, as evidenced by the upregulation of key BA transporters Shp and Bsep, along with the expected downregulation of the downstream target gene Cyp7a1. These well-characterized transcriptional changes confirm that the model responds appropriately to FXR activation [46].

As expected, mice fed a WD exhibited increased body and liver weights, along with elevated plasma aminotransferase levels. Steatosis and inflammatory cell infiltration were significantly increased in the WD group. However, OCA treatment had no measurable effect on any of these parameters in our study, which contrasts with prior studies reporting improvements in steatosis and inflammation under considerably higher dosing (30 mg/kg/day) and longer treatment duration [47].

Fibrosis represents an advanced stage of MASLD and is associated with significant adverse clinical outcomes. In our model, all patterns of mild-to-moderate metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis were recapitulated. WD feeding increased hepatic hydroxyproline levels [48], although the corresponding histological changes were not significantly ameliorated by OCA treatment. Moreover, while we confirmed elevated expression of fibrosis-associated genes (Tgfb1, TIMP1, Col1a2), OCA treatment did not confer any beneficial effect on these molecular markers. Similarly, apoptosis-related parameters, such as Panx1 and Bcl-2, were upregulated following WD—consistent with our previous findings [27], but remained unaffected by OCA treatment.

Given their central role in cellular energy metabolism, mitochondria are critically implicated in the pathogenesis and progression of MASLD. A comprehensive understanding of mitochondrial alterations throughout disease development is therefore essential, particularly for the identification of novel therapeutic targets [5,49]. FXR is a pivotal regulator of autophagy and mitochondrial turnover under both physiological and pathological conditions. In addition, FXR confers anti-oxidative and cytoprotective effects, largely through its regulation of mitochondrial function [12]. However, the clinical implications of FXR agonists in the treatment of MASLD remain insufficiently defined.

A comprehensive understanding of mitochondrial metabolism requires consideration of the simultaneous utilization of diverse substrates contributing electrons to the ETS. To evaluate mitochondrial respiration, we employed a combination of respiratory substrates and SUT respiratory protocols [5,49]. Several mitochondrial mechanisms have been implicated in the pathogenesis of MASLD, including reduced

activity of the ETC complexes [50]. Consistent with our previous findings, we confirmed that WD reduces succinate-activated mitochondrial respiration in WD-fed mice [5]. Moreover, our results demonstrated that OCA had no significant effect on pyruvate/malate-stimulated respiration, NADH-dependent respiration, or ketogenesis. β -oxidation, which has been reported to decrease by approximately 40%–50% in patients with MASH compared to lean individuals [51], was also unaffected in our study. Although it has been proposed that OCA, via FXR activation, enhances mitochondrial respiratory capacity in mouse liver organoids [52], this effect was not observed in our *in vivo* model.

As previously demonstrated, WD reduces the gene expression of the Sdh complex, likely as a protective mechanism against substrate overload [5]. We confirmed this finding, which is consistent with the reduced succinate-stimulated respiration (NADH + succinate) observed in our study. Notably, following OCA administration at 10 mg/kg/day, only Sdh subunits B and C were upregulated, with no effect on SDH activity, reflecting the limited capacity of OCA to enhance mitochondrial respiration. Furthermore, the downregulation of the Sdh modulator proteins Trap1 and Sucn1 by WD, as previously reported [27], was corroborated by our findings. In addition, both proteins exhibited a trend toward increased expression following OCA treatment at 10 mg/kg/day. Uncoupling proteins, located in the inner mitochondrial membrane, dissipate the proton gradient, resulting in reduced ATP synthesis [53,54]. In MASLD, the expression of Ucp2 is upregulated, likely as a compensatory mechanism to mitigate redox pressure on the ETC [55]. Moreover, excessive fatty acid load on the ETC increases ROS production, exacerbating oxidative stress and its associated consequences [56]. In our model, we confirmed a significant increase in Ucp2 expression in the WD group.

5. Conclusion

To our knowledge, this is the first study to comprehensively evaluate the metabolic effects of OCA in a Western diet-induced MASLD model, using high-resolution respirometry alongside detailed histological and molecular analyses.

In conclusion, while our study demonstrated that OCA modulated several genes associated with FXR activation, it did not translate into improvements in mitochondrial respiration or key pathological features, including steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis, in the mouse model of MASLD. Notably, OCA did not exert any adverse effects in the CD group, suggesting that OCA was well tolerated under physiological conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Melek: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pavla Staňková:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eva Peterová:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tumisang Edward Maseko:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Veronika Špalková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Reem Matar:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ahmed Ibrahim:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Moustafa Elkhalaf:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Miroslav Podhola:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Alžběta Štefela:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Zuzana Červinková:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Petr Pávek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Otto Kučera:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Funding

This research was supported by the Grant Agency of the Charles University, GA UK 488122 and SVV-2025-260776; the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic, AZV NU21-07-00550; and the ERDF Project, NETPHARM CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2025.118542](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2025.118542).

Data availability

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

References

- M. Eslam, P.N. Newsome, S.K. Sarin, Q.M. Anstee, G. Targher, M. Romero-Gomez, S. Zelber-Sagi, V. Wai-Sun Wong, J.F. Dufour, J.M. Schattenberg, T. Kawaguchi, M. Arrese, L. Valenti, G. Shiha, C. Tiribelli, H. Yki-Jarvinen, J.G. Fan, H. Gronbaek, Y. Yilmaz, H. Cortez-Pinto, C.P. Oliveira, P. Bedossa, L.A. Adams, M.H. Zheng, Y. Fouad, W.K. Chan, N. Mendez-Sanchez, S.H. Ahn, L. Castera, E. Bugianesi, V. Ratziu, J. George, A new definition for metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease: an international expert consensus statement, *J. Hepatol.* 73 (1) (2020) 202–209.
- Y. Li, P. Yang, J. Ye, Q. Xu, J. Wu, Y. Wang, Updated mechanisms of MASLD pathogenesis, *Lipids Health Dis.* 23 (1) (2024) 117.
- A.I. Legaki, I.I. Moustakas, M. Sikorska, G. Papadopoulos, R.I. Velliou, A. Chatzigeorgiou, Hepatocyte mitochondrial dynamics and bioenergetics in obesity-related non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 113 (2022) 126–143.
- X. Li, W. Chen, Z. Jia, Y. Xiao, A. Shi, X. Ma, Mitochondrial dysfunction as a pathogenesis and therapeutic strategy for Metabolic-Dysfunction-Associated steatotic liver disease, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 26 (9) (2025).
- P. Stankova, O. Kucera, E. Peterova, H. Lotkova, T.E. Maseko, K. Nozickova, Z. Cervinkova, Adaptation of mitochondrial substrate flux in a mouse model of nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21 (3) (2020).
- T. Zhang, Y. Nie, J. Wang, The emerging significance of mitochondrial targeted strategies in NAFLD treatment, *Life Sci.* 329 (2023) 121943.
- G. Serviddio, F. Bellanti, G. Vendemiale, E. Altomare, Mitochondrial dysfunction in nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *Expert Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 5 (2) (2011) 233–244.
- M. Shum, J. Ngo, O.S. Shirihai, M. Liesa, Mitochondrial oxidative function in NAFLD: friend or foe? *Mol. Metab.* 50 (2021) 101134.
- B.M. Forman, E. Goode, J. Chen, A.E. Oro, D.J. Bradley, T. Perlmann, D.J. Noonan, L.T. Burka, T. McMorris, W.W. Lamph, R.M. Evans, C. Weinberger, Identification of a nuclear receptor that is activated by farnesol metabolites, *Cell* 81 (5) (1995) 687–693.
- V. Massafra, A. Milona, H.R. Vos, R.J.J. Ramos, J. Gerrits, E.C.L. Willemsen, J. M. Ramos Pittol, N. Ijssennagger, M. Houweling, H. Prinsen, N.M. Verhoeven-Duijf, B.M.T. Burgering, S.W.C. van Mil, Farnesoid x receptor activation promotes hepatic amino acid catabolism and ammonium clearance in mice, *Gastroenterology* 152 (6) (2017) 1462–1476, e10.
- R.M. Gadaleta, K.J. van Erpecum, B. Oldenburg, E.C. Willemsen, W. Renoij, S. Murzilli, L.W. Klomp, P.D. Siersema, M.E. Schipper, S. Danese, G. Penna, G. Laverny, L. Adorini, A. Moschetta, S.W. van Mil, Farnesoid x receptor activation inhibits inflammation and preserves the intestinal barrier in inflammatory bowel disease, *Gut* 60 (4) (2011) 463–472.
- C.Y. Han, T.H. Kim, J.H. Koo, S.G. Kim, Farnesoid x receptor as a regulator of fuel consumption and mitochondrial function, *Arch. Pharm. Res.* 39 (8) (2016) 1062–1074.
- P.R. Maloney, D.J. Parks, C.D. Haffner, A.M. Fivush, G. Chandra, K.D. Plunket, K. L. Creech, L.B. Moore, J.G. Wilson, M.C. Lewis, S.A. Jones, T.M. Willson, Identification of a chemical tool for the orphan nuclear receptor FXR, *J. Med. Chem.* 43 (16) (2000) 2971–2974.
- B. Goodwin, S.A. Jones, R.R. Price, M.A. Watson, D.D. McKee, L.B. Moore, C. Galardi, J.G. Wilson, M.C. Lewis, M.E. Roth, A regulatory cascade of the nuclear receptors FXR, SHP-1, and LXR-1 represses bile acid biosynthesis, *Mol. Cell* 6 (3) (2000) 517–526.
- D.Q. Huang, H.B. El-Serag, R. Loomba, Global epidemiology of NAFLD-related HCC: trends, predictions, risk factors and prevention, nature reviews, *Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 18 (4) (2021) 223–238.
- G. Rizzo, D. Passeri, F. De Franco, G. Ciaccioli, L. Donadio, G. Rizzo, S. Orlandi, B. Sadeghpour, X.X. Wang, T. Jiang, M. Levi, M. Pruzanski, L. Adorini, Functional characterization of the semisynthetic bile acid derivative INT-767, a dual farnesoid x receptor and TGR5 agonist, *Mol. Pharm.* 78 (4) (2010) 617–630.
- F. Tacke, EASL-EASD-EASO clinical practice guidelines on the management of metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), *J. Hepatol.* (2024).
- A.J. Sanyal, R. Loomba, Q.M. Anstee, V. Ratziu, K.V. Kowdley, E.J. Lawitz, C. White, S. Sawhney, T. Capozza, R. Leyva, Final results from the phase 3 REGENERATE trial evaluating the effects of obeticholic acid in patients with pre-cirrhotic fibrosis due to metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis, (2024).
- F.D.A., Ocaliva (obeticholic acid) by Intercept Pharmaceuticals: Drug Safety Communication - Serious Liver Injury Being Observed in Patients without Cirrhosis, 2024. (<https://www.fda.gov/safety/medical-product-safety-information/ocaliva-obeticholic-acid-intercept-pharmaceuticals-drug-safety-communication-serious-liver-injury>).
- E.G. Bligh, W.J. Dyer, A rapid method of total lipid extraction and purification, *Can. J. Biochem. Physiol.* 37 (8) (1959) 911–917.
- D.E. Kleiner, E.M. Brunt, M. Van Natta, C. Behling, M.J. Contos, O.W. Cummings, L. D. Ferrell, Y.C. Liu, M.S. Torbenson, A. Unalp-Arida, M. Yeh, A.J. McCullough, A. J. Sanyal, Design and validation of a histological scoring system for nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, *Hepatology* 41 (6) (2005) 1313–1321.
- M.M. Bradford, A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding, *Anal. Biochem.* 72 (1–2) (1976) 248–254.
- R. Kand'ar, P. Zakova, H. Lotkova, O. Kucera, Z. Cervinkova, Determination of reduced and oxidized glutathione in biological samples using liquid chromatography with fluorimetric detection, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 43 (4) (2007) 1382–1387.
- T. Roušar, O. Kučera, H. Lotková, Z. Cervinková, Assessment of reduced glutathione: comparison of an optimized fluorometric assay with enzymatic recycling method, *Anal. Biochem.* 423 (2) (2012) 236–240.
- E. Gnaiger, Mitochondrial Physiology, Bioenergetics communications, 2020.
- S. Hartwig, J. Kotzka, S. Lehr, Isolation and quality control of functional mitochondria. *Mitochondrial Medicine: Volume I, Probing Mitochondrial Function*, Springer, 2015, pp. 9–23.
- P. Stanková, O. Kučera, E. Peterová, M. Elkalaf, D. Rychtmoc, J. Melek, M. Podhola, V. Zubaňová, Z. Červinková, Western diet decreases the liver mitochondrial oxidative flux of succinate: insight from a murine NAFLD model, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 22 (13) (2021).
- D. Brenner, Mechanisms of Fibrogenesis, *Experimental biology and medicine* (Maywood, N.J.) 233 (2008) 109–122.
- Y. Tie, F. Tang, D. Peng, Y. Zhang, H. Shi, TGF-beta signal transduction: biology, function and therapy for diseases, *Mol. Biomed.* 3 (1) (2022) 45.
- F. Xiao, S.L. Waldrop, A.K. Khimji, G. Kilic, Pannexin1 contributes to pathophysiological ATP release in lipooptosis induced by saturated free fatty acids in liver cells, *Am. J. Physiol. Cell Physiol.* 303 (10) (2012) C1034–C1044.
- B. Fromenty, M. Roden, Mitochondrial alterations in fatty liver diseases, *J. Hepatol.* 78 (2) (2023) 415–429.
- J. Kumar, M. Hasan, S. Mohsin, M.H. Alzahr, T. Nagar, A. Jamil, A. Ahmed, V. K. Lavu, S. Kumar, Assessing the efficacy of farnesoid x receptor agonists in the management of metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis: efficacy of farnesoid x receptor agonists in metabolic Dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease: systematic review and Meta-analysis, *Clin. Res. Hepatol. Gastroenterol.* 49 (2) (2025) 102530.
- F. Nevens, P. Andreone, G. Mazzella, S.I. Strasser, C. Bowlus, P. Invernizzi, J. P. Drenth, P.J. Pockros, J. Regula, U. Beuers, A placebo-controlled trial of obeticholic acid in primary biliary cholangitis, *N. Engl. J. Med.* 375 (7) (2016) 631–643.
- K.V. Kowdley, R. Vuppalanchi, C. Levy, A. Floreani, P. Andreone, N.F. LaRusso, R. Shrestha, J. Trotter, D. Goldberg, S. Rushbrook, G.M. Hirschfield, T. Schiano, Y. Jin, R. Pencek, L. MacConell, D. Shapiro, C.L. Bowlus, A.S. Investigators, a randomized, placebo-controlled, phase II study of obeticholic acid for primary sclerosing cholangitis, *J. Hepatol.* 73 (1) (2020) 94–101.
- D. D'Amato, A. De Vincentis, F. Malinverno, M. Viganò, D. Alvaro, M. Pompili, A. Picciotto, V.P. Palitti, M. Russello, S. Storato, M.G. Pigozzi, V. Calvaruso, E. De Gasperi, A. Lleo, A. Castellaneta, A. Pellicelli, N. Cazzagon, A. Floreani, L. Muratori, S. Fagioli, G.A. Niro, V. Feletti, R. Cozzolongo, N. Terreni, M. Marziani, R. Pellicano, P. Pozzoni, L. Baiocchi, L. Chessa, F. Rosina, G. Bertino, M. Vinci, A. Morgando, E. Vanni, G. Scifo, R. Sacco, M. D'Anto, V. Bellia, R. Boldizzoni, S. Casella, B. Omazzi, G. Poggi, L. Cristoferi, A. Gerussi, V. Ronca, R. Venerè, F. Ponziani, M. Cannavo, A. Mussetto, R. Fontana, F. Losito, E. Frassetto, M. Distefano, F. Colapietro, S. Labanca, G. Marconi, G. Grassi, G. Galati, S.E. O'Donnell, C. Mancuso, G. Mullinacci, A. Palermo, E. Claar, A. Izzi, A. Picardi, P. Invernizzi, M. Carbone, U. Versapiani-Gentilucci, P.B.C.R. Italian, P. B.C.S.G. The club epatologi ospedalieri /associazione italiana gastroenterologi ed endoscopisti digestivi ospedalieri, Real-world experience with obeticholic acid in patients with primary biliary cholangitis, *JHEP Rep.* 3 (2) (2021) 100248.
- FDA, Hepatic Decompensation and Failure in Primary Biliary Cholangitis Patients with Cirrhosis, 2022. (https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2022/207999s0081bl.pdf).
- J.E. Edwards, C. LaCerte, T. Peyret, N.H. Gosselin, J.F. Marier, A.F. Hofmann, D. Shapiro, Modeling and experimental studies of obeticholic acid exposure and the impact of cirrhosis stage, *Clin. Transl. Sci.* 9 (6) (2016) 328–336.

- [38] C. Lin, B. Yu, L. Chen, Z. Zhang, W. Ye, H. Zhong, W. Bai, Y. Yang, B. Nie, Obeticholic acid induces hepatotoxicity via FXR in the NAFLD mice, *Front Pharm.* 13 (2022) 880508.
- [39] Y. Xu, Y. Zhu, S. Hu, X. Pan, F.C. Bawa, H.H. Wang, D.Q. Wang, L. Yin, Y. Zhang, Hepatocyte miR-34a is a key regulator in the development and progression of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, *Mol. Metab.* 51 (2021) 101244.
- [40] Z.Y. Yang, F. Liu, P.H. Liu, W.J. Guo, G.Y. Xiong, H. Pan, L. Wei, Obeticholic acid improves hepatic steatosis and inflammation by inhibiting NLRP3 inflammasome activation, *Int J. Clin. Exp. Pathol.* 10 (8) (2017) 8119–8129.
- [41] C. Kunne, A. Acco, S. Duijst, D.R. de Waart, C.C. Paulusma, I. Gaemers, R.P. Oude Elferink, FXR-dependent reduction of hepatic steatosis in a bile salt deficient mouse model, *Biochim. Et. Biophys. Acta (BBA)Mol. Basis Dis.* 1842 (5) (2014) 739–746.
- [42] H. Jouihan, S. Will, S. Guionaud, M.L. Boland, S. Oldham, P. Ravn, A. Celeste, J. L. Trevasakis, Superior reductions in hepatic steatosis and fibrosis with co-administration of a glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist and obeticholic acid in mice, *Mol. Metab.* 6 (11) (2017) 1360–1370.
- [43] F. Haczejni, L. Poekes, H. Wang, A.R. Mridha, V. Barn, W. Geoffrey Haigh, G. N. Ioannou, M.M. Yeh, I.A. Leclercq, N.C. Teoh, G.C. Farrell, Obeticholic acid improves adipose morphometry and inflammation and reduces steatosis in dietary but not metabolic obesity in mice, *Obes. (Silver Spring)* 25 (1) (2017) 155–165.
- [44] I.P. Inc., OCALIVA (Obeticholic acid) 5 mg and 10 mg Tablets Product Monograph, Mississauga, ON, 2018.
- [45] B. Angelin, I. Björkhem, K. Einarsson, S. Ewerth, Hepatic uptake of bile acids in man. Fasting and postprandial concentrations of individual bile acids in portal venous and systemic blood serum, *J. Clin. Invest* 70 (4) (1982) 724–731.
- [46] L. Adorini, K. Rigbolt, M. Feigh, J. Roth, M. Erickson, Increased hepatoprotective effects of the novel farnesoid x receptor agonist INT-787 versus obeticholic acid in a mouse model of nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *PLoS One* 19 (4) (2024) e0300809.
- [47] K.S. Tolbol, M.N. Kristiansen, H.H. Hansen, S.S. Veidal, K.T. Rigbolt, M.P. Gillum, J. Jelsing, N. Vrang, M. Feigh, Metabolic and hepatic effects of liraglutide, obeticholic acid and elafibranor in diet-induced obese mouse models of biopsy-confirmed nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *World J. Gastroenterol.* WJG 24 (2) (2018) 179–194.
- [48] Z.M. Ding, Y. Xiao, X. Wu, H. Zou, S. Yang, Y. Shen, J. Xu, H.C. Workman, A. L. Osborne, H. Hua, Progression and regression of hepatic lesions in a mouse model of NASH induced by dietary intervention and its implications in pharmacotherapy, *Front Pharm.* 9 (2018) 410.
- [49] E. Gnaiger, Mitochondrial pathways and respiratory control: an introduction to OXPHOS analysis, *Bioenerg. Commun.* 2020 (2020) 2, 2.
- [50] M. Pérez-Carreras, P. Del Hoyo, M.A. Martín, J.C. Rubio, A. Martín, G. Castellano, F. Colina, J. Arenas, J.A. Solís-Herruzo, Defective hepatic mitochondrial respiratory chain in patients with nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, *Hepatology* 38 (4) (2003) 999–1007.
- [51] M.P. Moore, R.P. Cunningham, G.M. Meers, S.A. Johnson, A.A. Wheeler, R. R. Ganga, N.M. Spencer, J.B. Pitt, A. Diaz-Arias, A.I.A. Swi, G.M. Hammoud, J. A. Ibdah, E.J. Parks, R.S. Rector, Compromised hepatic mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation and reduced markers of mitochondrial turnover in human NAFLD, *Hepatology* 76 (5) (2022) 1452–1465.
- [52] J.M. Ramos Pittol, A. Milona, I. Morris, E.C.L. Willemsen, S.W. van der Veen, E. Kalkhoven, S.W.C. van Mil, FXR isoforms control different metabolic functions in liver cells via binding to specific DNA motifs, *Gastroenterology* 159 (5) (2020) 1853–1865, e10.
- [53] K.D. Chavin, S. Yang, H.Z. Lin, J. Chatham, V.P. Chacko, J.B. Hoek, E. Walajtys-Rode, A. Rashid, C.H. Chen, C.C. Huang, T.C. Wu, M.D. Lane, A.M. Diehl, Obesity induces expression of uncoupling protein-2 in hepatocytes and promotes liver ATP depletion, *J. Biol. Chem.* 274 (9) (1999) 5692–5700.
- [54] R.A. Memon, G.S. Hotamisligil, S.M. Wiesbrock, K.T. Uysal, R. Faggioni, A. H. Moser, K.R. Feingold, C. Grunfeld, Upregulation of uncoupling protein 2 mRNA in genetic obesity: lack of an essential role for leptin, hyperphagia, increased tissue lipid content, and TNF-alpha, *Biochim Biophys. Acta* 1484 (1) (2000) 41–50.
- [55] G. Serviddio, F. Bellanti, R. Tamborra, T. Rollo, N. Capitanio, A.D. Romano, J. Sastre, G. Vendemiale, E. Altomare, Uncoupling protein-2 (UCP2) induces mitochondrial proton leak and increases susceptibility of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) liver to ischaemia-reperfusion injury, *Gut* 57 (7) (2008) 957–965.
- [56] C. Koliaki, M. Roden, Alterations of mitochondrial function and insulin sensitivity in human obesity and diabetes mellitus, *Annu Rev. Nutr.* 36 (2016) 337–367.